

Network Programmability for Smart Factory Mobile Robotics: the SmartEdge Project Approach

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Abstract: P4-based network programmability is exploited to enable swarm formation and reliable communications in decentralized smart factory scenarios including mobile robots. In band telemetry will be extensively used by all network nodes to provide for dynamic aggregation/disaggregation of connected entities to perform different augmented functions: computing, massive data-delivery, time-sensitive networking.

1. Introduction

The SmartEdge project seeks to enable the dynamic integration of decentralised edge intelligence, for smart IoT applications, ensuring reliability, security, privacy and scalability. This will be realized via a framework for autonomous intelligent swarms featuring real-time semantic integration, discoverability, and composability.

The decentralized swarm intelligence will leverage on P4-based network programmability to accelerate functionalities such as automatic discovery and dynamic network swarm formation in near real time, embedded network security and isolation, and hardware-accelerated in-network operations for context-aware networking [1].

The P4 language was introduced to define and program the data plane pipelines and functions of an SDN switch or a network interface card [2]. Data plane programmability includes, besides a custom pipeline (sequence of SDN match-action tables), configurable dataset (packet header, metadata), workflows (control), functions (actions) and stateful objects, allowing complex packet manipulation and processing procedures currently not available in standard SDN switches and that would require the intervention of the SDN controller.

P4 allows the definition of custom parser section enabling the implementation of proprietary or novel protocol headers, the enforcement of complex operations on the fields and values of the packets and on flow control and forwarding functions (e.g., packet cloning, replication and recirculation in the pipeline, in band telemetry- INT). Furthermore, stateful objects allow for the definition of finite state machines inside the switch and describe complex states over which further forwarding selections or packet manipulations can be performed. P4 is substantially independent with respect to the data plane platform. That is, the same P4 program can be applied on different devices including software switches, ASICs, network cards, and edge nodes [3].

In this work, P4 network programmability for decentralized swarm intelligence is investigated in the context of the SmartEdge smart factory scenario, which includes heterogeneous computing and networking devices, such as cameras, network gateways, mobile robots, and edge computing nodes.

2. Smart factory scenario

The reference smart factory facility manufactures a range of enterprise IT products, such as servers and storage arrays. It currently employs robots and cobots [4] as part of the production process and uses Autonomous Mobile Robots (AMRs) [5, 6] to move components and products around the facility. The components and products are typically loaded into specially designed caddies or mobile racks. The AMRs take products off conveyer belts at the end of the production lines and position them in specific locations in mobile racks. Multiple mobile racks need to be available at a location, as products have different physical characteristics. When the racks have the correct allocation of products loaded, they are taken away by other AMRs to the next stage in the manufacturing process. AMRs typically have sensors, e.g., LiDAR and bumper sensors, to aid them in moving around known environments and comply with health and safety requirements, but have limited onboard intelligence, and so need to operate in well-defined operational areas. Typically, fixing the location and orientation of mobile equipment, e.g., mobile racks, is achieved by locking

them into large fixed frames and installing guardrails, which allows the AMR to navigate the operational area via consistent predefined paths. Therefore, the fixed infrastructure solves the location consistency problem for the AMRs, but at the expense of flexibility and efficiency. Additionally, as the AMR's sensors have limited fields of view, detection of unexpected objects in the AMR's operational area is sometimes incomplete.

Research has been done to enable AMRs to operate in uncertain environments, but surprisingly relatively little on collaboration and problem solving in factories. This may be due to the preference of employing fixed infrastructure solutions to remove the uncertainty rather than the challenge of giving robots more intelligence to operate in an uncertain world. Figure 1 shows an example of the target smart factory operational area operating in an uncertain environment and implementing the concept of decentralized swarm intelligence.

A number of different AMRs and edge devices collectively form a swarm. Some devices may exclusively be part of one swarm, whereas others may participate in multiple swarms; they may be permanently assigned to a specific swarm or only part of the swarm for a certain period of time. The AMRs and edge devices perform different functions to collectively move products around the operational area and the broader manufacturing facility. The AMRs and edge devices communicate over WiFi or private 5G network, via a specialised SmartEdge router. As the SmartEdge swarm formation and management is performed in the P4 network layer, each AMR and edge device will have a P4 processing component, either built into a smart network card or run as a P4 software module. This will ensure that all devices can directly participate and communicate with any other device in the swarm. In theory any device could coordinate the formation and management of the SmartEdge swarm, but in practice these functions will tend to gravitate to devices with greater compute power.

Fig. 1: Smart factory utilising P4 network layer swarm formation and management.

3. Requirements for swarm networking

In this section we report the detailed set of requirements identified to support decentralized swarm intelligence and swarm networking in the context of the P4-empowered smart factory scenario.

1. the ability to discover other devices and their capabilities and enlist them into the swarm;
2. the ability to communicate through the network layer to other devices in the swarm;
3. the ability to exit the swarm in a controlled manner;
4. the ability of the swarm to automatically recover if a swarm device is unexpectedly lost;
5. maintain the swarms cohesiveness, or devices “stickiness” to the swarm;
6. where a device is part of two or more swarms, there must be no cross over between the data and control planes between the swarms, i.e. each swarm must remain isolated even if a device is shared;
7. swarm specific communication between devices in a swarm must not pass outside of the swarm;
8. if a device leaves a swarm, it should no-longer receive internal swarm communications;
9. a device joining a swarm should receive all internal swarm communications;

10. a channel must exist for swarms to communicate with devices outside of a swarm, e.g. to reach available devices and enlist them into the swarm;
11. communications emanating from the swarm should appear to come from the swarm and not a specific device, i.e. the internal structure of the swarm should not be ascertainable from its external communications.

4. P4 data plane programmability for swarm formation

Figure 1 depicts the strategic direction of automatic swarm formation, which involves providing data plane programming capability using P4 Language to all components in the factory, including mobile robots, racks, cameras, and IoT edge gateways [7]. This allows for efficient processing of necessary communications between these components using P4 [8]. For example, if cameras detect an unexpected object in their area and require urgent action, a P4-programmed protocol message can be sent to trigger appropriate responses. Similarly, if mobile robot 1 intends to load rack 1 with a specific trajectory, a message must be sent to other robots in the area to prevent collisions. However, mobile robot 1 may not have knowledge of which robots are present in the area. Hence, P4 programmability plays a crucial role in detecting the elements within the area through detailed camera images and location information from other mobile robots, and facilitating communication of relevant messages. Subsequently, the swarm intelligence system can analyze the received messages and inform the algorithm that controls the motion planning of the robots. The algorithm takes into consideration the position of the detected object and adjusts the motion plans of nearby robots to avoid collisions. This could involve slight alterations in the motion plans of one robot, slowing down of another, or even temporary halting of a robot for a brief period. The integration of swarm intelligence with P4 ensures that the components in the factory work cohesively to minimize the risk of collisions and facilitate effective communication among different elements. This can significantly enhance the productivity and efficiency of the factory by facilitating seamless data sharing and collaboration among devices. Ultimately, this collaborative approach can substantially reduce the occurrences of downtime, incidents, and other issues that may arise in industrial settings.

4.1. Swarm discovery and inclusion

In order to discover other devices, including their capabilities, and enlist them into the swarm intelligence system, the P4-based system may be programmed as follows: 1. Defining a custom discovery protocol using P4 that allows mobile robots, racks, cameras, and IoT edge gateways to exchange discovery messages periodically with each other to build a network topology. This protocol should define the format and semantics of the messages, including fields for device capabilities (such as whether the device is a robot, a camera, or an IoT edge gateway, and what sensors, actuators, or processing capabilities it has) and its location. 2. Programming the wireless programmable switches using P4 to listen for discovery messages on the wireless network and to extract the relevant metadata about device capabilities and locations. The switches should also update their forwarding tables based on the location information of the devices, in order to facilitate communication within the swarm intelligence system. 3. Using the extracted capability and location metadata to build a logical map of the factory floor that can be used by the swarm intelligence system to coordinate the activities of mobile robots, racks, cameras, and IoT edge gateways.

Implementing the protocol in P4 could involve defining the message headers and fields, as well as the processing logic in the P4 switch. For example, a P4 switch could use a combination of match-action tables and stateful processing to route discovery messages to their destination devices, as shown in Figure 2(a).

4.2. Controlled swarm exit

To allow mobile robots or other devices to exit the swarm intelligence system in a controlled manner the: 1. Using the previous discovery protocol to signal their intention to exit. This message will include fields for the identity of the device, any pending tasks, and other necessary contextual information. 2. Programming the wireless programmable switches in the network with P4 to listen for the custom control messages for exiting devices. The switches should remove the exiting devices from their forwarding tables to prevent any further communication between them and the other devices in the swarm intelligence system. By using P4 to create this custom control message format, devices in the swarm intelligence system can communicate with each other effectively and efficiently. This helps ensure that all devices are aware of each other's intentions and can adapt to changes in the system in real-time. By including specific information, such as pending tasks, the system can ensure that any unfinished work is reassigned to other devices, preventing work duplication or lost work, as shown in Figure 2(b).

Fig. 2: Swarm operation: swarm discovery and joining (a), controlled exit (b), unexpected exit and recovery (c).

4.3. Unexpected swarm exit and recovery

To enable the swarm intelligence system to automatically recover if a swarm device is unexpectedly lost, the following steps can be taken: 1. Define a mechanism to detect when a device is lost, such as by using a telemetry system with IoT edge gateways and cameras that can report on the status of the devices within the network. This mechanism should identify when a device is no longer responding or is otherwise experiencing issues. 2. Program the wireless programmable switches using P4 to update their forwarding tables and topology information to exclude the lost device's information automatically. The switches should reroute traffic to other available devices in the system to ensure efficient communication. 4. Configure the swarm intelligence system to initiate automated routines to replace the lost device with a new device so that it can integrate into the swarm intelligence system as a backup. By defining and implementing suitable mechanisms to detect lost devices and automated error remediation routines using the P4 language architecture, devices within the network can continue to work even in the presence of device loss. These implementations can enable network-wide fault tolerance and resiliency, which can lead to a more reliable and efficient swarm intelligence system, as shown in Figure 2(c).

4.4. Cohesiveness, isolation

A P4-based swarm telemetry system (either in-band or out-of-band) is able to check the presence and status of the mobile robots or other devices within the swarm intelligence system, allowing it to maintain its cohesiveness. The monitoring of the swarm intelligence system continuously for signs of deviations from optimal performance to detect disconnections from mobile robots or other devices. Key metadata metrics are in this case: a) the geolocation information of the device, that may be used to forecast its trajectory and allowing anticipating future swarm operation, and b) the device state, for example in terms of battery level or computational resources.

Swarm isolation can be achieved using a firewall or whitelist programmed in P4 that can filter out swarm-specific communication. Specific header fields identify swarm-specific communication (e.g., swarm ID, device ID, and message type). Each outgoing message from a swarm device must contain these header fields. Additional match-action tables look for these header fields and take action based on the information they contain. A firewall function can be programmed to drop any messages that contain swarm-specific header fields if they are detected outside of the swarm, by relying on geolocation metadata. This approach can help protect the swarm from outside attacks and preserve the integrity of data exchanged within the swarm.

5. Preliminary deployment and research directions

The focus of the first phase of the research activity has been to implement an experimental environment where to adapt and test the programmability paradigm for the considered scenario.

A general purpose x86 board (cite APU1) has been considered for the implementation of the P4 switches. The board has been formatted with Ubuntu OS and equipped with a dual band (i.e., 2.4GHz and 5GHz) miniPCIe Qualcomm DAXA-F1 chipset QCA9980 radio module providing three chains, for MIMO techniques. Each board natively provides three Ethernet interfaces.

The wireless channels have been realized by mean of the 802.11a standard (e.g., @5GHz). In order to create slave interfaces for the P4 switch, two options have been evaluated: (i) the configuration of pure transparent wireless links with the Wireless Distribution System (WDS) technique, or (ii) by creating overlay interfaces (i.e., VXLAN) over

the normal AP-station connections. The first solution has been analysed, adoption the nl80211 driver for the WDS configuration. The WDS protocol is based on the adoption of the 4-mac-addresses for the transmission of the packets. By adding the local mac address is possible to overcome the local domain visibility of the standard AP, allowing the transmission also from and to hosts not directly attached to the wireless segment and speeding up the forwarding time. In the considered implementation with nl80211 driver, client side the physical interface will be used, while AP side a virtual interface will be activated for each WDS-enabled connected client.

To implement the P4 switch a dockerized Bmv2 software switch implementation has been considered. The instantiated docker container has the visibility of the host namespace, being able to access the active interfaces. The Bmv2 software has been extended in order to support the dynamicity of the wireless link. In fact, the Bmv2 software has been designed to handle wired interfaces (copper and/or fiber) and was not ready to support the deactivation of the interfaces (when a WDS link goes down, the virtual interface at the AP side is removed). This limitation has been resolved, allowing the Bmv2 software to not crash under those conditions. The grpc-based P4runtime interface towards the P4 SDN controller has been activated.

For the P4 SDN controller implementation, a custom lightweight solution, based on the python *p4runtime* library has been considered. In this case the topology events are generated by the nodes, in a distributed fashion, and the controller is only responsible for the pushing of the flow-entries according to the considered pipeline. The in band telemetry (INT) paradigm has been considered, augmenting the forwarded packets with additional information, including the quality of the link (i.e., RSSI), the residual battery load, (da completare la lista a seconda dello scenario considerato). The structure of the INT header has been redefined, reducing the byte occupancy to not overload the bandwidth of the radio links.

Acknowledgements: This work is supported by the European Union's Horizon RIA research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101092908 (SmartEdge).

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